

Studies on Oxazoles. Part I : Synthesis and Chlorination of Some new 2-Amino-4-substituted Oxazoles and their Use as Fungicides

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Some new 2-amino-4-substituted oxazoles synthesised by condensing various ketones with urea and using either bromine or iodine as the condensing agent, have been subsequently chlorinated to yield the respective 5-chloro oxazole derivatives which have been assayed for their fungicidal activity against *Piricularia oryzae* (Cav.) the causative organism of rice plant, as the test fungus. A relation between fungitoxicity and chemical structure has been explored.

THE chemistry¹⁻³ and wide range of pharmacological properties of oxazole derivatives like hypertensive⁴, analgesic, antiinflammatory^{5,6}, antibacterial, antiviral⁷, antitubercular⁸, anticonvulsant⁹, urinary tract infections¹⁰ and similar such diseases have been cited in the literature.

The method of preparation of oxazole, first reported by Cornforth and Cornforth¹¹ has been subsequently modified.^{12,13} Since then many new methods of synthesising the substituted oxazoles have been developed¹⁴. One of the methods of synthesising the 2-amino-, and 2-*N*-substituted amino oxazoles is by the reaction of various alpha-haloketones with urea¹⁵. The relative inaccessibility of the alpha-haloketones is a major draw back of this method for its general use in preparing these oxazoles.

In view of this, an attempt has been made to find out the appropriate conditions under which 2-amino oxazoles can be synthesised using simple and readily available starting materials.

The present paper deals with the synthesis of some 2-amino-4-substituted oxazoles from urea and an appropriate ketone using either bromine or iodine as the condensing agent.

It has been observed that both bromine and iodine are able to bring about this reaction. But bromine is found to be more effective as regards the time of condensation as well as the yield of the end product.

It is well known that, chloro compounds belonging to the azole class are commercially used as fungicides¹⁶. In view of this fact the parent oxazoles prepared here have been chlorinated with dry chlorine gas in acetic acid medium after protecting the amino group by forming the corresponding hydrochloride salts. In each case, a monochloro derivative resulted.

In an identical type of reaction, in case of 2-amino-4-substituted thiazoles, the chlorine atom has been found to occupy C₅ position as the activity of this position is maximum, more so, when there is a polar substituent at C₂ position¹⁷. In that case, it has been shown that the polar effect of the substituents at C₂ and C₄ position¹⁸ direct the incoming chlorine atom to C₅ position of the thiazole nucleus. This assumption gains further support from the fact that when 2-amino-4-aryl thiazoles are brominated, 5-bromo thiazoles are resulted in each case. The bromine does not occupy any other position except C₅ of the thiazole moiety¹⁹ even though there are activating oxygenated group in the phenyl nucleus attached to C₄ position.

In analogy with the above established experimental observations, in the case of the oxazoles, the chlorine atom is assumed to have occupied the C₅ position which is free and is most active. In case of the 2-amino oxazoles, the orienting effect of the -NH₂ group enhances the activity of C₅ position; this being the para-position with respect to the -NH₂ group.

That the activity of the C₅ position is maximum has also been established from the following facts. The reaction of oxazoles with electrophiles shows that the order of reactivity is C₅ > C₄ > C₂ and bromination of oxazole ring is in conformity with this²⁰. A consideration of the charge densities at these positions shows position 5 to be slightly more reactive than position 4 and electrophilic attack at these positions is facilitated when the ring is activated by electron donating substituent like -NH₂ group. Hence in the chlorination of the 2-amino-4-substituted oxazoles, the chlorine atom has assumed to have occupied position 5 as the position 4 is already blocked and the activity of position 5 has been enhanced due to the -NH₂ group at position 2.

That the chlorine atom goes to position 5 is further supported on the following experimental observations. When 2-amino-4-phenyl oxazole is treated with diazotised aniline, coupling reaction takes place giving rise to an orange coloured azo dye in which the phenyl azo group is linked to the C₅ position of the oxazole moiety. But 2-amino-4-phenyl-5-chloro oxazole resulted from the chlorination of the above oxazole fails to undergo coupling reaction at all which indicates that in the later case C₅ is not free and is blocked by the chlorine atom. When the chloro oxazole is refluxed for ten hours with HCl (1:3) and allyl alcohol the original chlorine free oxazole is obtained which responds to the diazo coupling reaction.

Experimental

1. 2-Amino-4-phenyl oxazole :

In a clean and dry conical flask, acetophenone (6 g) was taken. To it bromine (8 g) in dry benzene (40 cc) was added very slowly in small proportion while keeping the flask in sun light. The mixture was vigorously shaken till the colour due to bromine was discharged. To this solution, urea (15 g) was added. The flask was fitted with a double surface

reflux condenser and the mixture was refluxed in a water bath for 27 hrs. The condenser was removed and the mixture was further heated for a period of 3 hrs. The reaction product was then cooled, repeatedly extracted with ether to remove the unreacted ketone and bromine to save it from becoming gummy. The product was then basified with conc. ammonia and kept over night. It was then filtered and the product was repeatedly washed with water, dried and finally recrystallised from water : alcohol (1:1 v/v).

Comparative study with Br₂ and I₂ as condensing agent in different solvents.

Reactants	Solvents	Period of heating in hours	Colour	Yield %
Urea + Acetophenone + bromine	Benzene	24	Light yellow	55
-do-	-do-	30	-do-	60
-do-	D.M.F.	30	-do-	60
Urea + Acetophenone + iodine	-do-	30	-do-	20
-do-	Benzene	30	-do-	20

The compounds showed the same m.p., m.m.p. and super imposable IR curve with a peak at 1555 cm⁻¹, characteristic of the -N=C-O- ring stretching frequency. The homogeneity and purity of the compounds were tested through tlc. The compounds were developed on a thin layer of silica gel-H having a slurry thickness of 250μ by the ascending technique and after development the compounds were detected as fluorescent spots under U.V. light. The R_f values of the compounds were found to be same (R_f 0.81 in benzene-methanol, 50 : 50 v/v; and 0.89 in benzene-isoamyl alcohol, 50 : 50 v/v).

The colour, yield, m.p. and analytical data of such 2-amino-4-substituted oxazoles are given in Table-1(Sl no.1 to 10).

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	Nature of R	Colour	Yield (%)	M.P. °C	Cl. (%)		N (%)		Fungicidal result Parts in ppm for 50% germination.
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -	L.Y.	60	140	-	-	16.85	17.50	15
2.	p-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ -	L.Y.	50	190	17.85	18.25	13.80	14.39	5
3.	p-Hydroxy C ₆ H ₄ -	G.Y.	50	205	-	-	15.45	15.90	15
4.	o-OH C ₆ H ₄ -	B	50	167	-	-	15.38	15.90	15
5.	p-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	Y.B.	45	180	-	-	14.62	14.73	14
6.	α-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	B	60	112	-	-	13.61	13.33	7.5
7.	β-C ₁₀ H ₇ -	Y.B.	80	162	-	-	13.73	13.33	6
8.	p-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	B	56	190	-	-	-	-	15
9.	p-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ -	Y	65	160	-	-	15.57	16.09	24.5
10.	C ₄ H ₉ S-	B	70	90*	-	-	16.62	16.86	12.5

L=Light, Y=Yellow, G=Green, B=Brown

* Denotes decomposition.

2. 2-Amino-4-phenyl-5-Chloroxazole :

2-Amino-4-phenyl oxazole(2 g) was treated with conc. HCl (3ml) and the hydrochloride salt formed was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (25 ml). To this solution, dry chlorine gas was passed in a slow and steady rate. The deep colour of the solution gradually faded. The chlorination was continued till solid separated out. The reaction mixture was poured into water and the precipitate was then basified and kept over-night. The chloro oxazole formed was then filtered, washed with water till it was free from chlorine, then dried and recrystallised from alcohol : water (1 : 1 v/v). The colour, yield, m.p. and analytical data of the chloro oxazoles are given in Table-2.

- (b) The presence of chlorine augments fungicidal activity and this increases with increase in the no. of chlorine atoms in the molecule.
- (c) The presence of α -naphthyl and β -naphthyl groups at position 4 increases fungicidal activity.
- (d) The presence of $-\text{CH}_3$ and $-\text{NO}_2$ groups does not help towards fungitoxicity. The deactivating effect of $-\text{NO}_2$ group is well compensated by introduction of chlorine atom.
- (e) When substituent like $-\text{OH}$ group is present in the aryl nucleus at C_4 position in the chloro derivatives the compounds are very much active.

TABLE-2

Sl. No.	Nature of R	Colour	Yield (%)	M.P. °C	Cl. (%)		N (%)		Fungicidal result
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Parts in ppm for 50% germination.
1.	C_6H_5-	L.Y.	83	205	17.91	18.25	13.92	14.39	3.0
2.	$p\text{-Cl.C}_6\text{H}_4-$	Y.	80	155	30.85	31.00	11.85	12.22	1.5
3.	$p\text{-OH.C}_6\text{H}_4-$	Y.B.	65	183	16.71	16.86	12.93	13.30	1.0
4.	$o\text{-OH.C}_6\text{H}_4-$	B.	60	126	16.69	16.86	12.89	13.30	5.0
5.	$p\text{-OCH}_3.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$	G.W.	82	225	15.68	15.81	12.11	12.47	8.3
6.	$\alpha\text{-C}_{10}\text{H}_7-$	C.B.	85	105	14.38	14.51	11.01	11.45	4.3
7.	$\beta\text{-C}_{10}\text{H}_7-$	Gr.	85	149	14.31	14.51	11.10	11.45	4.3
8.	$p\text{-NO}_2.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$	B	72	175	14.71	14.82	17.21	17.53	4.2
9.	$p\text{-CH}_3.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-$	L.Y.	85	164	16.98	17.02	13.21	13.42	16.0
10.	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{S}-$	B	80	>250	17.50	17.70	13.73	13.96	8.3

L=Light, Y=Yellow, G=Green, B=Brown, W=White, C=Chocolate, Gr=Grey.

Fungicidal Test :

The synthesised oxazoles and the chloro oxazoles have been assayed for their fungicidal activities against *Piricularia oryzae* (Cav.), the causative organism of rice blast, as the test fungus. The method of Montgomery and Moore²¹ with slight modification was used for the fungicidal assay of these compounds. The spores were kept in contact with the chemicals at different dilutions for 24 hrs and the percentage of germination was studied in that duration. The dilution in p.p.m. of the compounds for 50 per cent germination of the fungus has been given in Table-1. The analysis of the fungicidal results showed a definite in pattern existing between fungitoxicity and the chemical structure in general. The following generalisations in this respect may be derived.

- (a) Both the oxazole and the chloro oxazoles have got considerable fungicidal activity, in general against *Piricularia oryzae*(Cav.) while compounds of Sl.no.2, 6, 7, of Table 1 and 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7 and 8 of Table 2 are very active.

- (f) Heterocyclic group like thienyl at C_4 position does not seem to enhance fungicidal activity.

- (g) The order of activity of the substituents at position 4 in the oxazoles is $-\text{Cl.C}_6\text{H}_4 > -\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7 > -\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{S} > -\text{OCH}_3.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4, -\text{NO}_2.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4, -\text{C}_6\text{H}_5, -\text{OH.C}_6\text{H}_4 > -\text{CH}_3.\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$.

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References

1. J. W. CORNFORTH, "Heterocyclic compounds", Vol. 5, R. C. ELDER field, Ed., Wiley, New York, 1956.
2. R. H. WILEY, *Chem. Rev.*, 1945, 37, 401.
3. J. W. CORNFORTH, "The Chemistry of Penicillin" Princeton Univ. Press, Princeton, N. J., 1949.

PATTANAYAK ROUT & MAHAPATRA : STUDIS ON OXAZOLES. PART I : SYNTHESIS & CHLORINATION ETC.

4. Laboratories Dausse, S. A. Britt. Pat., *Chem. Abs.*, 1963, 69, 59220.
5. G. CRANK, Brit. Pat., 1972, 1,264,258; *Chem. Abs.*, 1972, 76, 126963.
6. JOHN WYETH & BROTHERS Ltd., French, Pat.; *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, 74, 53765.
7. I Ito, S. MURAKAMI & K. KATO, Japan Pat., 1970, 70, 15, 733, *Chem. Abs.*, 1970, 73, 77240.
8. G. CARRARA, F. M. CHIANCONE, V.D. AMATO, E. CINOUTHIACE, C. MARTINUZZI, U.M. TEOTINO and N. VISCONTI; *Gazz. Chem.*, Ital, 1952, 82, 652.
9. P. E. SAETER and U. H. LINDBERG; U.S. Patent; 1968, 3, 401, 172, 1968; *Chem. Abs.* 69, 106694.
10. SCHNITZER, *J. Pharmacol. Exptl., Therap*: 1946, 88, 47.
11. J. W. CORNFORTH and R. H. CORNFORTH; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 96.
12. H. BREDERECK and R. H. BANGERT; *Angew Chem. Inst. Ed. Engl.*, 1962, 1,662.
13. H. BREDERECK and R. BANGERT; *Chem. Ber.*, 1964, 97, 1414.
14. Ignatius, J. Turchi and Michaeli J. S. Dewar; *Chem. Rev.*, 1975, 75, 389.
15. R. GOMPPER and O. CHRISTMANN; *Chem. Ber.*, 1959, 92, 1944.
16. *Pesticide Manual*, pp. 195, Brit. Pat., 999, 097.
17. E. OCHIAE and Y. KASHIDA; *J. Pharm. Soc.*, (Japan), 1942, 62, 97.
18. TAKEDA, *J. Pharm. Soc. (Japan)* 1947, 63, 193.
19. G. N. MAHAPATRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 33, 527.
20. R. GOMPPER and H. RUHLE; *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1959, 626, 92.
21. H. B. S. MONTGOMERY and M. H. MOORE; *J. Pomol & Hort. Sci.*, 1938, 15, 253.